

WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF SCHOOL TEACHERS AND THEIR SATISFACTION TOWARDS THEIR JOB

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Abstract: Work life balance is one of the most challenging issues being faced by the schoolteachers in the 21st century because of the type of roles they play at home and the spillover of personal life over work life. This study explores the relationship between age and dimensions used for work-life balance among schoolteachers. The objective is to examine how different age groups of teachers perceive various aspects related to work-life balance and job satisfaction. Data was collected from 116 schoolteachers in different age groups: Below 30 years, 31-40 years, 41-50 years, and Above 50 years. The dimensions assessed include work interference with personal life, personal life interference with work, work-personal life enhancement, level of acceptance on work-life balance, job satisfaction, and attributes of job satisfaction. The results reveal that younger teachers (below 30 years) experience lower work interference with personal life compared to older age groups. However, personal life interference with work does not vary significantly across age groups. On the other hand, older teachers (above 50 years) report higher work-personal life enhancement and a higher level of acceptance on work-life balance than younger teachers. Age does not have a significant impact on overall job satisfaction or the perception of job satisfaction attributes among schoolteachers. The findings highlight the importance of age-related considerations in understanding teachers' work-life balance experiences. Younger teachers may benefit from interventions that address work interference with personal life, while older teachers may appreciate measures that enhance their work-personal life balance and promote acceptance of work-life balance practices. These insights can guide educational institutions and policymakers in tailoring strategies to meet the specific needs of teachers across different age groups, ultimately fostering a more balanced and satisfying work environment for school educators.

Keywords: Work life balance, School teachers and Job satisfaction
JEL Classification Number : M10,M12

1 Introduction to the Concept of The Study

The field of education plays a vital role in shaping the future of society, and at the heart of this endeavor are dedicated school teachers. These educators tirelessly invest their time, energy, and passion into nurturing young minds, inspiring creativity, and imparting

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knowledge that can positively influence generations to come. However, the demands of the teaching profession, coupled with the responsibilities of personal life, often pose significant challenges to achieving work-life balance for these educators. This delicate balance between their professional commitments and personal well-being profoundly impacts their job satisfaction and overall quality of life.

Work-life balance, a term often used to describe the equilibrium between work-related activities and personal life, is a multifaceted concept. For schoolteachers, it involves managing their responsibilities within the classroom while still attending to personal needs, relationships, and interests. However, the contemporary educational landscape presents unique challenges that can tip this balance and affect their job satisfaction.

One of the primary challenges faced by schoolteachers is the interference of work with their personal life. As they invest time and energy in lesson planning, grading papers, and attending to extracurricular activities, teachers may find it difficult to dedicate adequate time to personal matters. This imbalance can lead to neglecting personal needs, putting personal life on hold, and even experiencing conflicts between work and non-work activities.

Conversely, personal life can also interfere with their work. Teachers who face personal issues, such as family problems or health concerns, may find it challenging to maintain their energy and effectiveness in the classroom. Balancing the demands of work while navigating personal challenges can lead to decreased job satisfaction and potential burnout.

Despite these challenges, there are factors that can enhance the work-life balance of schoolteachers. When personal life is fulfilling and energizing, it can positively impact their work performance. A supportive and nurturing personal life can provide teachers with the motivation and enthusiasm needed to excel in their profession. Additionally, when teachers are satisfied with their job, it can spill over into their personal lives, creating a positive feedback loop of fulfillment and contentment.

Job satisfaction among schoolteachers is influenced by a multitude of factors, some of which are specific to the education system. Issues such as a lack of control over their work, inadequate recognition for their efforts, job insecurity, fear of layoffs, harassment, and age discrimination can contribute to decreased job satisfaction. Moreover, inadequate pay and limited promotion opportunities may also affect their sense of professional accomplishment and recognition.

The social dynamics within the school environment can also play a significant role in shaping a teacher's job satisfaction. Isolation from fellow school teachers, either physically

or psychologically, can lead to feelings of disconnection and hinder opportunities for collaboration and support.

This study explores the complex interplay between work-life balance, job satisfaction, and the challenges faced by schoolteachers in their pursuit of personal and professional fulfillment. It delves into the factors that contribute to work-life interference and identifies strategies to achieve a healthier equilibrium between the demands of teaching and personal well-being. By understanding the intricacies of this critical issue, policymakers, educational institutions, and teachers themselves can work together to create a more conducive and satisfying environment for those who dedicate their lives to nurturing the minds of future generations.

2. Review of Literature

Workers in small construction organizations were found to be handled directly and personally by the firm owner or manager, and they had access to informal work-life supports that were offered on a "as needs" basis, according to the findings published by Helen Lingard, Michelle Turner, et.al., (2015). at contrast, employees at medium-sized enterprises experienced higher levels of work pressure and an expectation that the job would be prioritized over family life. Furthermore, the assumption that the work would take priority over family life was very prevalent.

Researchers Sadaf Naz et.al., (2017) investigated students' opinions of the influence that working has on their life in relation to the duties associated with their schoolwork. Interviews using a semi-structured format were used to gather data from ten female professors who worked in a university located in the northern part of Pakistan. The data were analyzed using a method called thematic analysis. According to the findings, the vast majority of academics find it difficult to maintain a healthy balance between their obligations at home and at work. Participants struggled with a variety of issues both at home and at their places of employment, which had an effect on their lives in both settings. These issues included an absence of assistance and facilities at home as well as at the place of employment. However, it did not seem that these issues would prevent them from continuing to fulfill both their professional and domestic obligations. In order to maintain this equilibrium, the participants used a number of techniques, such as separating out and scheduling time for schoolwork, ensuring the support of their families, and making more efficient use of the time they spent at work. On the other hand, it seemed that this had the unintended consequence of these academics having very little time for themselves, either in the form of leisure time or time that was completely committed to their own mental and physical welfare. The findings of this study have significant repercussions for

people who are employed, their families, their employers, and the policymakers in Pakistan and other nations with circumstances comparable to Pakistan's.

The purpose of this research by Megan A. O'Mahony (2019) was to investigate the experiences of foreign students who were physically and temporally isolated from their families about the study-work-life balance. Several themes were uncovered via the use of thematic analysis on the data gleaned from ten semi-structured interviews conducted with postgraduate students. These changes included alterations in boundary management owing to the competing demands of job and school as well as variances in time zones. In addition, students reported facing social and personal problems (in terms of the expectations of their families, maintaining relationships, and socializing in the nation in which they were staying). Students, many of whom were strongly dependent on their own family network for support, contributed to their own social retreat and isolation by isolating themselves because of the time constraints. The results provided support for the hypothesis that the time difference has an effect on the way in which foreign students control their boundaries and interact with their social environments.

Shalini M. (2017) found a few variables that have a substantial effect on the work-life balance (WLB) of female instructors working at KLE S. Nijalingappa college in the Rajajinagar suburb of Bangalore. The college is located in Bangalore. According to the conclusions of the study, there are a number of factors and challenges that have an effect on both the professional and personal lives of the 45 female teachers who are employed by KLE SNC. These factors and challenges have an effect on both aspects of their lives. The numerous professional and personal concerns that have an effect on the work-life balance of school teachers were investigated and given a lot of attention in this study. The findings of the study focused light on the many challenges and roadblocks that educators need to overcome in order to achieve WLB. According to the results of the study, it is necessary for the organization to initiate initiatives to promote work-life balance in order to improve the performance of school teachers and to guarantee that school teachers are happy. The study indicated that management take action to decrease the number of hours that employees spend working overtime in order to enhance the overall quality of teaching and put a larger focus on instruction rather than administrative obligations. It was recommended that management take action to reduce the number of hours that employees spend working overtime in order to improve the overall quality of instruction.

Vasumathi (2018) conducted a literature review on the subject of work life balance (WLB) of school teachers with regard to the significance of WLB, theories of WLB, determinants of WLB, facilitators of WLB, coping strategies of WLB, WLB and performance, and finally, consequences of WLB. are employed in all manufacturing and service sectors

throughout the world. school teachers are one of these types of workers. In many developed countries, women are confronted with a variety of challenges, some of which include sexual and mental harassment in the workplace, worries regarding the safety of traveling in various modes of transport after working institution hours, the requirement for flexible working hours and childcare facilities, resistance from members of their own families, and bias based on gender in promotional policies and decision making. In addition to these worries, many individuals who have jobs find it difficult to properly balance the demands of their dual responsibilities (work and family) and to find answers to the day-to-day challenges that they face in both their professional and their personal life. People will be able to live a peaceful life in both their jobs and with their families, which will pave the way for the rapid development and growth of the nation. When everyone who is working receives the support of their family members, organizations, and government policies for their problems, and when those working take the appropriate steps to rectify their various issues in order to strike a balance between their work and life, it will result in people being able to live a peaceful life in both their work and their families.

Dhaval et al., (2019) conducted a study to determine the extent to which teaching professionals at a Mangalore college maintain a healthy work-life balance. The findings of the research also shed light on the aspects that might contribute to an improved work-life balance. The organization's school instructors are an invaluable resource in their respective fields. Students and faculty members alike are the pillars upon which each institution is built. Both the students and the professors at an institution have an equal responsibility for maintaining their own mental health in order to ensure the institution's continued success. Because of the rapidly increasing costs of living in our world, going to work has become an absolute must. our, in turn, results in personal development, which, in turn, leads to the expansion of the organization and the improvement of the family's financial situation. They are the very essence of existence. It is of the utmost importance that everyone working in the organization must be happy; failure to do so would result in a detrimental influence on each and every family member, most notably on their children, who are referred to as "the future generation." Even though educational institutions were created to be free of stress, stress levels among teachers are nevertheless high owing to the imbalance between their professional and personal lives.

Sonia DelroseNoronha et.al., (2019) identified the gap in the literature as well as the prerequisite for carrying out this study. The information for the research came from a wide range of publications, including journals, papers, books, websites, doctoral theses, and periodicals. According to the findings of the survey, the schoolteachers' professional responsibilities take up a disproportionate amount of their time, leaving less time for their personal lives. Because of this, educators are forced to sacrifice their personal time to

complete work-related responsibilities, which upsets the work-life balance they strive for. According to the findings of several research studies, an individual's ability to strike a healthy balance between their professional and personal lives may change at various points during their career.

3. Need of The Study

Having some degree of control over one's job is essential to achieving a healthy balance between work and life. When a person's right to a fulfilling existence both within and outside of paid labor is acknowledged and regarded as the norm, it will have been accomplished. This will be to the joint advantage of the individual, business, and society as a whole. Work-life balance refers to the practice of developing and sustaining work environments that are supportive of employees' health and well-being. This will help school teachers to have a balance between their professional and personal duties, which will in turn increase school teachers' loyalty and productivity. This served as inspiration for the researcher to proceed with the study. The research focuses on how school instructors manage their time between work and their personal lives. The purpose of the research is to determine the many factors that contribute to high stress levels and an unbalanced work-life balance.

4. Statement of Problem

Employers are obligated to develop programs that will not only help them recruit and retain school teachers for longer periods of time but also boost their overall productivity in their jobs. The schools provide a wide variety of services and amenities to its employees, including transportation, canteens, and day care facilities, amongst many others. Postal savings initiatives, etc. Provide information regarding the work-life balance rules and special leave arrangements, such as annual leave and public holiday leave, career break leave, leave for elected representatives, and leave to appear as a witness in court in your company; provide flexible working hours and part-time employment; allow employees to choose their own work schedules; Health care centers, rewards and recognition, career growth, insurance plans, job rotation, incentives, and performance-relative pay; Provide information regarding the work-life balance rules and special leave arrangements, such as annual leave and public Even though schools are working toward the fulfillment of school teachers' demands, there may be a mismatch between those wants and the difficulties school teachers have in terms of striking a good balance between their professional and personal lives in terms of keeping a healthy work-life balance. Because of this, the task that lies ahead of the study is to explore the school teachers' capacity to strike a good balance between their personal and professional lives.

5. Objectives of The Study

1. To study the demographic profile of the respondents
2. To identify the factors that affects the quality of life in terms of career and family.
3. To discuss school teachers comfort in work-life balance issues with employers.
4. To evaluate the satisfaction of job among school teachers working in the schools based on their work life.
5. To analyze the attributes of school teachers towards work life balance.

6. Research Methodology

6.1 Research design: Descriptive research design.

6.2 Source of data:

Primary data: The primary data was collected from school teachers, through structured questionnaire. Secondary data: Websites, Journals, and from Library.

6.3 Sample design: Simple random sampling.

6.4 Sample Size: Out of 150 samples collected from the respondents 116 were valid and thus the sample size of the study is fixed at 116.

6.5 Statistical tools used: Percentage analysis, Descriptive statistics and oneway anova. Mean score value

7. Limitations of The Study

It is possible that the sample size of the research was restricted owing to time and resource restrictions, which may influence the results' ability to be generalized.

The data acquired via surveys and interviews may be vulnerable to self-reporting bias, which occurs when individuals offer comments that are seen to be socially acceptable.

External variables, such as school policies and socio-economic situations, may have an impact on the work-life balance of teachers as well as the level of job satisfaction they experience, but these aspects may not have been adequately accounted for in the research.

8. Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Demographic variables of the respondents

Demographic variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Age	Below 30 years	61	52.6
	31 – 40 years	31	26.7
	41 – 50 years	12	10.3
	Above 50 years	12	10.3
	Total	116	100
Type of family	Joint	3	2.6
	Nuclear	113	97.4
	Total	116	100
House hold income	<10,000	11	9.5
	10,001-20,000	19	16.4
	20,001-30,000	41	35.3
	30,001-40,000	10	8.6
	40000 and above	35	30.2
	Total	116	100

The data shows that the majority of the respondents are below 30 years old, accounting for 52.6% of the total sample. The second largest group comprises respondents aged between 31 to 40 years, representing 26.7% of the sample. The proportion of respondents in the age groups of 41-50 years and above 50 years is relatively smaller, each accounting for 10.3% of the total respondents. Majority of respondents (97.4%) come from nuclear families, whereas only a small percentage (2.6%) come from joint families. The distribution of household income among the respondents shows that the largest group falls within the income range of 20,001-30,000, accounting for 35.3% of the total respondents. The second-largest group has a household income of 40,000 and above, representing 30.2% of the sample. Other income groups have relatively smaller proportions of respondents. Regarding household income, a significant portion of the respondents (35.3%) falls within the income range of 20,001-30,000, followed by 30.2% of respondents with a household income of 40,000 and above.

Table 2 Work interference with personal life

	Mean	SD
WIP 1	2.44	1.113
WIP 2	3.28	1.454
WIP 3	3.03	1.087
WIP 4	2.61	1.070
WIP 5	2.95	1.215
WIP 6	2.83	1.121
WIP 7	2.65	.877

The data indicates that, on average, respondents agree that their personal life is affected by work. They tend to experience difficulties in their personal life due to job demands, neglect their personal needs, and put their personal life on hold for work-related commitments. Respondents also feel the impact of work on their personal activities and need to juggle between work and non-work responsibilities. Furthermore, they perceive that they have limited time for non-work activities. Overall, the findings highlight the challenges teachers face in balancing their work and personal life.

Table 3 Personal life interference with work

	Mean	SD
PII 1	2.70	.998
PII 2	2.97	1.149
PII 3	2.92	1.073
PII 4	2.58	.815

The data indicates that respondents, on average, agree that their personal life interferes with their work. They feel that their personal life impacts their energy and effectiveness at work. Additionally, they report suffering at work due to personal life issues and find it hard to work because of personal matters. The findings highlight the challenges teachers face in maintaining a balance between their personal and professional lives and how these personal life aspects can affect their work performance and well-being.

Table 4 Work personal life enhancement

	Mean	SD
WPL 1	2.95	1.062
WPL 2	2.88	1.006
WPL 3	2.60	1.149
WPL 4	3.04	.964

The data indicates that respondents tend to "Agree" that there is a mutual enhancement between their personal life and work. They feel that their personal life gives them energy for their job and, in turn, their job gives them energy to pursue personal activities. They also perceive that their personal life contributes to a better mood at work, and their job positively influences their overall mood. These findings suggest that a positive relationship between work and personal life can lead to increased energy and better moods in both domains, which can have a beneficial impact on overall well-being and job satisfaction.

Table 5 Job satisfaction of school teachers

Particulars	Mean	SD
JS 1	3.22	1.209
JS 2	3.33	.949
JS 3	3.46	1.247
JS 4	3.34	.960
JS 5	2.96	1.247
JS 6	3.14	1.338
JS 7	2.58	1.073
JS 8	2.94	1.129
JS 9	3.24	1.191
JS 10	4.57	7.760

The data suggests that school teachers, on average, tend to have some level of dissatisfaction or concerns regarding certain aspects of their job satisfaction. These aspects include lack of control over their work, job insecurity, fear of layoffs, harassment, lack of respect from supervisors, age discrimination, inadequate pay, and isolation from fellow schoolteachers. However, they also express some level of satisfaction in terms of the recognition they receive for their work.

It is important to note that job satisfaction is a complex and multifaceted construct, and individual experiences and perceptions may vary significantly among school teachers. These findings can serve as valuable insights for educational institutions and policymakers to identify areas for improvement and develop strategies to enhance the overall job satisfaction and well-being of schoolteachers.

Table 6 Comparison between age and dimensions used for work life balance with school teachers

Ho1: No relationship is there between age and dimensions used for work life balance with schoolteachers

		N	Mean	SD	F	Sig
Work interference with personal life	Below 30 years	61	2.5821	.57411	6.012	0.001
	31 – 40 years	31	2.9723	.88362		
	41 – 50 years	12	3.0858	.68218		
	Above 50 years	12	3.3342	.47950		
	Total	116	2.8163	.71649		
Personal life interference with work	Below 30 years	61	2.7008	.66743	2.039	0.113
	31 – 40 years	31	2.7661	.61215		
	41 – 50 years	12	3.1042	.63477		
	Above 50 years	12	3.0417	.46262		
	Total	116	2.7953	.64065		
Work personal life enhancement	Below 30 years	61	2.7295	.65875	3.744	0.013
	31 – 40 years	31	2.8629	.55842		
	41 – 50 years	12	3.1042	.69461		
	Above 50 years	12	3.3542	.73437		
	Total	116	2.8685	.66795		
Level of acceptance on work life balance	Below 30 years	61	2.9164	.57942	3.916	0.011
	31 – 40 years	31	3.1194	.51473		
	41 – 50 years	12	3.3583	.55671		
	Above 50 years	12	3.3667	.47354		
	Total	116	3.0629	.57127		
Job satisfaction	Below 30 years	61	3.0836	.71465	.793	0.500
	31 – 40 years	31	3.0419	.43572		
	41 – 50 years	12	3.3333	.66652		
	Above 50 years	12	3.2333	.62134		
	Total	116	3.1138	.63546		
Attributes of job satisfaction	Below 30 years	61	3.2408	.84389	1.472	0.226
	31 – 40 years	31	3.2952	.50959		
	41 – 50 years	12	3.3742	1.02470		
	Above 50 years	12	3.7492	.67924		
	Total	116	3.3217	.77903		

Work Interference with Personal Life:

The F-value is 6.012, and the significance level is 0.001 ($p < 0.05$).

There is a significant relationship between age and work interference with personal life.

Teachers below 30 years report lower work interference with personal life compared to teachers in older age groups.

Personal Life Interference with Work:

The F-value is 2.039, and the significance level is 0.113 ($p > 0.05$).

There is no significant relationship between age and personal life interference with work. Teachers across different age groups tend to have similar perceptions of personal life interference with work.

Work-Personal Life Enhancement:

The F-value is 3.744, and the significance level is 0.013 ($p < 0.05$).

There is a significant relationship between age and work-personal life enhancement.

Teachers above 50 years report higher work-personal life enhancement compared to younger age groups.

Level of Acceptance on Work-Life Balance:

The F-value is 3.916, and the significance level is 0.011 ($p < 0.05$).

There is a significant relationship between age and the level of acceptance on work-life balance.

Teachers above 50 years show higher acceptance levels of work-life balance compared to younger age groups.

Job Satisfaction:

The F-value is 0.793, and the significance level is 0.500 ($p > 0.05$).

There is no significant relationship between age and job satisfaction.

Teachers across different age groups tend to have similar levels of job satisfaction.

Attributes of Job Satisfaction:

The F-value is 1.472, and the significance level is 0.226 ($p > 0.05$).

There is no significant relationship between age and the attributes of job satisfaction.

Teachers across different age groups tend to have similar perceptions of job satisfaction attributes.

Interpretation Summary:

Work Interference with Personal Life: Younger teachers (below 30 years) tend to experience less work interference with their personal life compared to older age groups.

Personal Life Interference with Work: There is no significant difference in personal life interference with work among teachers of different age groups.

Work-Personal Life Enhancement: Older teachers (above 50 years) report higher levels of work-personal life enhancement compared to younger teachers.

Level of Acceptance on Work-Life Balance: Teachers above 50 years show higher acceptance levels of work-life balance compared to younger teachers.

Job Satisfaction: Age does not have a significant impact on overall job satisfaction among school teachers.

Attributes of Job Satisfaction: Age does not significantly influence the perception of job satisfaction attributes among school teachers.

These findings suggest that age plays a role in certain dimensions of work-life balance and job satisfaction among school teachers. However, it does not have a significant impact on overall job satisfaction or the perception of job satisfaction attributes. The results highlight the importance of addressing specific age-related factors when designing interventions and policies to improve work-life balance and job satisfaction among teachers.

9. Findings

- Maximum of the respondents are from the age group of below 30 years.
- Most of the respondents are from nuclear family.
- Maximum of the respondents are earning from 20001 to 30000.
- Most of the respondents agree about their personal life.
- Maximum of the respondents strongly disagree about difficulty in personal life because of job.
- Most of the respondents agree towards neglecting personal needs.
- Maximum of the respondents agree towards neglecting personal needs.
- Most of the respondents are neutral about putting personal life on hold for work.

10. Suggestions

- The vast majority of respondents voiced their disagreement with the statement that having a job creates difficulties in one's personal life. For this reason, the schools may provide counseling and can run stress management programs for the schoolteachers so that they will be able to maintain a healthy balance between their personal lives and their professional lives without experiencing any stress.
- The non-work activities may be expanded by producing a circular inside the businesses for engaging in leisure events held by the schools, which leads to a clear image of controlling their nature of work with the organization. This leads to an increase in the amount of time that employees spend away from work.
- The schools should place a greater emphasis on the corporate governance that is associated with the performance evaluation of the schools so that the efficiency of their work may be enhanced in the foreseeable future.
- In order to maintain a healthy balance between work and life, schools have to consider the workloads of educators. Every person should be treated as special and distinctive, and organizations should make the effort to accommodate their employees' specific requirements. The ability of school teachers to maintain a healthy work-life balance

should merit an increase in pay. In order to lessen the amount of conflict that occurs at schools, the organization should expand initiatives that promote work-life balance.

- Human resources policies that can be used to increase work-life balance include providing a limited number of days of paid leave per year for child care, elder care, or personal problems; having policies around weekend and evening use of laptops and mobiles; and implementing time off in lieu of overtime pay arrangements. Other policies that may be utilized to promote the work-life balance include offering a restricted number of days of paid leave each year for the purpose of caring for children, caring for elderly family members, or dealing with personal issues.

11. Conclusion

The conclusion is that schools need to consider the workloads of instructors in order to strike a healthy balance between their personal and professional lives. Every person should be treated as special and distinctive, and organizations should make the effort to accommodate their employees' specific requirements. The ability of schoolteachers to maintain a healthy work-life balance should merit an increase in pay. To lessen the amount of conflict that occurs at schools, the organization should expand initiatives that promote work-life balance.

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